

Shivaji University, Kolhapur
Department of Commerce and Management
Research Advisory Committee (RAC)
Date: 24/05/2022

Sr. No	Name of the Candidate	Name of the Guide	Title of the study	Remark
8.	MR. GANESH SHIRANG NALE	Dr. VIDYA S. KADAM	" A STUDY OF WORKFORCE DIVERSITY, EQUITY AND INCLUSION (DEI) IN THE WORKPLACE AND ITS EFFECT ON WORK ENVIRONMENT WITH RESPECT TO THE HEALTHCARE INDUSTRIES IN PUNE DISTRICT"	<p>The committee has recommended to revise the draft synopsis in the light of following points:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Revise the proposal thoroughly. 2. Change the title as " A STUDY OF WORKFORCE DIVERSITY, EQUITY AND INCLUSION (DEI) IN THE WORKPLACE AND ITS EFFECT ON WORK ENVIRONMENT WITH RESPECT TO THE HOSPITALS IN PUNE DISTRICT" <p>The candidate has to revise draft synopsis and present it before next RAC</p>

Prof. (Dr.). S. S. Mahajan

Prof. (Dr.). A. M. Gurav

Dr. K. V. Marulkar

Dr. S. S. Bholia

Dr. A.K.Patil

Research Guide

Received the Copy of report

Date :

Signature of Candidate

The Candidate has submitted the revised draft of thesis/ dissertation/synopsis.

Date :

Signature